

APPENDIX S1

Discussion of Taxonomic Findings for Pseudocrenilabrinae and its Close Relatives

Here we provide a detailed discussion of our main taxonomic findings in the context of previous studies. To facilitate comparisons with figures and discussion in the main text, we refer to tribal groupings using the same informal acronyms outlined in Figs. 1 and 2. Many of these are commonplace in the cichlid phylogenetic literature. Informally recognized tribal assemblages or sub-groupings are referred to using lower case and the suffix “ines” (e.g., haplotilapiines, austrotilapiines, serranochromines). Quotation marks are used to denote taxa awaiting formal description or whose current generic assignment is questionable. Quotations are also placed around the genus name for taxa that fall outside of the clade containing the type species for that genus in our, or previous, analyses.

While taxon sampling across the entire Pseudocrenilabrinae is necessarily limited, we have sought to provide representation of as many previously recognized tribes as possible, with a focus on an enhanced representation of the so-called West/Central African (WCA) and former-tilapiine lineages at the base of the haplotilapiine radiation. For the great majority of tissue samples used in the study we have confirmed identifications by careful examination of voucher specimens, but for the few tissue loans received we rely on curatorial identification by the lending institution (voucher references available in Table S1).

Non-Cichlid Blenniiformes

Higher-order (i.e., intrafamilial and above) Blenniiformes (*sensu* Ghezelayagh et al. 2021, formerly Ovalentaria) relationships have proven difficult to resolve (but see Ghezelayagh et al.

2021). Despite limited sampling, as in previous studies, we recover a strongly monophyletic Atherinoidei (*sensu* Ghezelayagh et al. 2021, formerly Atherinomorpha) and a well-supported unnamed clade consisting of Mugilidae, Pomacentridae, Pseudochromidae, and Tripterygiidae (Miya et al. 2003, Setiamarga et al. 2008, Wainwright et al. 2012, Near et al. 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Betancur et al. 2017, Eytan et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017, Hughes et al. 2018, Ghezelayagh et al. 2021). While internal relationships are inconsistent between our concatenated and species trees and with some previous findings, intrafamilial relationships in our species tree agree with those recently recovered in Ghezelayagh et al.'s (2021) phylogeny based on hundreds of ultraconserved elements.

Both morphological and molecular work hypothesized a nested placement of the enigmatic Engineer blenny *Pholidichthys* (Family: Pholidichthyidae) within or close to “labroids” (Stiassny & Jensen 1987), but its position as sister to cichlids remained elusive (Sparks & Smith 2004) until Wainwright et al. (2012). A Cichlidae+Pholidichthyidae sister relationship has since been corroborated by several multilocus (Near et al. 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Betancur et al. 2017, Matschiner et al. 2017) and two phylogenomic (Eytan et al. 2015, Ghezelayagh et al. 2021) studies. With some adjustments to the assembly process (see methods and discussion in main text) we obtained amongst (Ghezelayagh et al. 2021) the largest number of loci for Pholidichthyidae to date. Both concatenated and gene tree analyses provide unequivocal support for a Pholidichthyidae+Cichlidae sister relationship, despite elevated gene tree conflict at this node.

Placement of the South American leaf fishes (Polycentridae) has also been difficult in previous studies (Wainwright et al. 2012, Eytan et al. 2015, Betancur et al. 2017, Matschiner et al. 2017). Although not unambiguously supported, our findings strongly favour a grouping of Polycentridae as sister to Cichlidae+Pholidichthyidae (Ghezelayagh et al. 2021). The nested

position of a marine lineage (Pholidichthyidae) amongst freshwater lineages (Polycentridae and Cichlidae) suggest a freshwater origin for cichlid fishes, contrary to what has been generally assumed in most discussions of cichlid biogeography (e.g., see Matschiner et al. 2017 for a recent discussion).

Cichlidae: Subfamily Relationships

As expected, the four cichlid subfamilies form robustly supported monophyletic clades consistent with disjunct continental distributions. Some multilocus data has produced a grouping of the two Indo-Malagasy subfamilies (Farias et al. 1999, Sparks 2003, Sparks 2004) but most support a basal divergence of the Indo-Malagasy Etroplinae followed by the Malagasy Ptychochrominae (Streelman & Karl 1997, Farias et al. 2000, Sparks & Smith 2004, Genner et al. 2007, Friedman et al. 2013, McMahan et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, this study). Reciprocal monophyly of the Neotropical Cichlinae and African Pseudocrenilabrinae is widely supported by molecular data (Farias et al. 1999, 2000, Sparks & Smith 2004, Genner et al. 2007, Friedman et al. 2013, McMahan et al. 2013, Keck & Hulsey 2014, Matschiner et al. 2017, 2020, this study).

Cichlidae: Etroplinae and Ptychochrominae

Internal relationships for the two Indo-Malagasy subfamilies were mostly congruent with previous multilocus phylogenies, except for our recovery of a paraphyletic *Ptychochromoides*. In both concatenated and species trees we find a *Ptychochromoides betsileanus*+*Katria katria* group sister to *Ptychochromis*, to the exclusion of *Ptychochromoides itasy*. Most multilocus phylogenies (Sparks 2003, Sparks 2004, Sparks 2008, Sparks et al. 2012, McMahan et al. 2013) and several

anatomical features (Stiassny & Sparks 2006, Sparks 2008) instead support a monophyletic *Ptychochromoides* sister to a *Katria*+*Ptychochromis* clade. The large multilocus dataset (40 loci) of Matschiner et al (2017) is the only other study to produce a *Ptychochromoides*+*K. katria* grouping. *Katria* is found near the northern limits of the distribution of *P. betsileanus* (Sparks 2004), so their grouping with larger molecular datasets and in the majority of gene trees in our study could be evidence of persistent historical gene flow in this region. Additional population-level studies are necessary to assess gene flow amongst these taxa.

Cichlidae: Pseudocrenilabrinae

Monophyly of Pseudocrenilabrinae is unambiguously supported by molecular data (Farias et al. 1999, 2000, Sparks & Smith 2004, Genner et al. 2007, Friedman et al. 2013, McMahan et al. 2013, Keck & Hulsey 2014, Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019, Matschiner et al. 2020, this study). Our analyses support the monophyly of all included tribes, except for Tilapiini in restricted cases (see below). We provide a robust hypothesis for most intertribal relationships and tribal assemblages, despite very high gene heterogeneity at some nodes. Shallower intratribal relationships are mostly well resolved, but some challenges remain in clarifying relationships within recent, rapidly evolving species flocks.

West/Central African (WCA) Lineages

Within Pseudocrenilabrinae early divergences gave rise to the predominantly riverine West/Central African tribes: Heterochromini, Tylochromini, Chromidotilapiini, Pelmatochromini, and Hemichromini (referred to herein as the WCA lineages).

The placement of Heterochromini within Pseudocrenilabrinae was challenged by morphological (Stiassny 1987, 1990, Lippitsch 1995, Kullander 1998) and some molecular (Farias et al. 1999, Keck & Hulsey 2014) data, but the majority of molecular studies support its position as sister to the remaining African lineages (Farias et al. 2000, Klett & Meyer 2002, Sparks & Smith 2004, Genner et al. 2007, Smith et al. 2008, López-Fernández et al. 2010; Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, McMahan et al. 2013, Keck & Hulsey 2014, Matschiner et al. 2017, Ilves et al. 2018, Irisarri et al. 2018, Matschiner et al. 2002, this study). We document moderate gene heterogeneity at the node connecting Heterochromini to the remaining Pseudocrenilabrinae, an observation that is in line with Keck & Hulsey's (2014) documentation of conflicting gene histories with a smaller dataset, indicating that both morphological homoplasy and gene heterogeneity likely contributed to past challenges in placing the tribe.

As in previous multilocus studies, monophyly of the widespread genus *Tylochromis* (Stiassny 1990) is strongly supported, as is its sister relationship to the remaining Pseudocrenilabrinae (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Matschiner et al. 2020). Very low gene heterogeneity is documented at the node supporting this placement of Tylochromini with some support for hybridization with Chromidotilapiini (Fig. 3a). Interestingly, *Tylochromis* are maternal mouthbrooders, an “advanced” reproductive strategy unique amongst WCA lineages but widespread among H-lineage taxa. The genus is comprised of 18 described species, however intrageneric relationships are currently poorly known. Detailed investigation of this early diverging, geographically widespread lineage holds considerable potential for understanding of biogeographic patterns across the continent.

Monophyly of remaining WCA tribes has been verified numerous times, but various alternative hypotheses with mixed support have been proposed regarding their interrelationships and placement with respect to the large pan-African haplotilapiines (Sparks 2003, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schlieven 2013, McMahan et al. 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Schwarzer et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019). Some multilocus phylogenies proposed Chromidotilapiini (Schwarzer et al. 2011, Friedman et al. 2013, Schwarzer et al. 2015) or some other less commonly inferred combination of WCA tribes as sister to the haplotilapiines (McMahan et al. 2013). Both our gene tree and concatenated analyses strongly favour a Pelmatochromini+Hemichromini clade as the sister to the haplotilapiines. A close relationship between these three lineages was alluded to in earlier work, but has been difficult to corroborate as a result of incomplete sampling of WCA tribes (Streelman & Karl 1997, Mayer et al. 1998, Streelman et al. 1998, Dunz & Schlieven 2013) or weak support at this node (Stiassny & Schlieven 2003, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019). A recent AHE phylogeny (Irisarri et al. 2018) is the only other study to provide unequivocal support for a Hemichromini+Pelmatochromini clade as sister to the haplotilapiines. Longstanding challenges at the node linking the WCA lineages and haplotilapiines are probably related to ancestral polymorphisms and/or genetic exchange, as suggested by the high levels of gene tree conflict (Figs 2e) and hybrid networks (Fig. 3a,b) revealed here.

Internal relationships of the polytypic WCA tribes reveal at least two non-monophyletic genera. Our recovery of paraphyletic *Pelmatochromis* and polyphyletic *Chromidotilapia* are consistent with previous multilocus phylogenies (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Schwarzer et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017). Hence the need for taxonomic revision of these WCA genera is underscored by our phylogenomic data.

WCA Lineages: Chromidotilapiini

Schwarzer et al. (2015) provided the most thoroughly sampled phylogenetic hypothesis for the largest of the WCA lineages, the Chromidotilapiini. Our topologies are mostly congruent and contribute added support for deep nodes. Like Schwarzer et al. (2015) we recover a basal split between two clades with nearly non-overlapping geographical distributions. The smaller of the two comprises *Chromidotilapia sensu stricto*, *Divandu* and *Parananochromis*, while the large clade contains the remaining genera and “*Chromidotilapia*”. Largely allopatric distributions between diverging lineages supports vicariance as an early driver of diversification (Schwarzer et al. 2015).

We also provide strong support for the inclusion of the *Teleogramma* within Chromidotilapiini. Placement of *Teleogramma* within Pseudocrenilabrinae (Myers 1939, Lippitsch 1995, Stiassny 1997, Takahashi & Nakaya 2002) or even within Cichlidae (Boulenger 1899) eluded researchers until relatively recently (Schwarzer et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017). Like the few other studies that include *Teleogramma* along with several other Chromidotilapiini, we support its placement near the root of the large clade (Schwarzer et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017).

Cytonuclear discordance (Schwarzer et al. 2015) and elevated gene tree heterogeneity (this study) reveal a history of ILS and hybridization in Chromidotilapiini (Fig. 3b,c). Short branches near the base (Fig. S1) are consistent with rapid diversification, likely related to the early colonization of newly available habitats, as well as hybridization, perhaps facilitated by past hydrological connections between west and central Africa (Schwarzer et al. 2015).

Haplotilapiines

Dunz & Schliewen (2013) provided a phylogeny-based revision for the haplotilapiine lineages formerly assigned to the catch-all Tilapiini (*sensu* Poll 1986 minus Boulengerochromini, Takahashi 2003; referred to herein as the former-tilapiines). This revision saw the creation of seven new tribes and description or re-description of several genera. Monophyly of the new tribes has been verified by molecular studies (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019, this study) and in some cases also by morphological synapomorphies (reviewed in Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017). Most molecular phylogenies agree with the early branching of the monotypic Etiini, followed by the former-tilapiine Oreochromini, then the remaining former-tilapiine tribes, and finally the EAR clade (Schliewen & Stiassny 2003, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018). However, conflicting hypotheses have been proposed for the interrelationships of most former-tilapiine tribes (minus Oreochromini) and their relationship to the EAR clade.

Haplotilapiines: Former-Tilapiines: Oreochromini

Oreochromini comprises all of the mouthbrooding former-tilapiines and notably includes the geographically restricted Barombi Mbo and *Alcolapia* species flocks, the commercially important “genera” *Oreochromis* and *Sarotherodon*, *Danakilia* from the Danakil Depression of Eritrea and Ethiopia, the geographically disjunct *Tristramella* of the Jordan Valley and *Iranocichla* from southern Iran.

Based on shared morphological attributes Trewavas (1983) hypothesized a close relationship between the geographically isolated *Danakilia* and *Iranocichla*. Efforts to extract

DNA from *Danakilia* had been unsuccessful (Stiassny et al. 2010) until (Schwarzer et al. 2016, Chiozzi et al. 2017), but the firm placement of its presumed sister *Iranocichla* and close relative *Tristamella* remained uncertain (Klett & Meyer 2002, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Schwarzer et al. 2016). Schedel et al. (2019) placed *Danakilia* within Oreochromini using mtDNA, but did not evaluate its sister relationship to *Iranocichla*. Our study provides corroborating phylogenomic support for the placement of *Danakilia* within Oreochromini and provides the first molecular affirmation of its sister relationship to *Iranocichla*. Unfortunately, we have been unable to include *Tristamella* within our analyses, and are unable to confidently determine whether the *Iranocichla*+*Danakilia* clade is sister to all other Oreochromini (Schedel et al. 2019, our species tree), closely related to the *Alcolapia*+“*Oreochromis*” clade (our concatenated tree) or closely related to the “*Sarotherodon*”+Barombi Mbo clade (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017). Network analyses suggest that hybridization between *Iranocichla* and an early oreochromine ancestor (Fig. 3d) and/or between the clades containing the Barombi Mbo and *Alcolapia* radiations (Fig. 3e) may be the root cause of challenges in the placement of *Iranocichla*+*Danakilia*+*Tristamella*. Given the extra-continental distribution of these intriguing endemic genera and the persistent uncertainty regarding their relationship to other Oreochromini, our study underscores the importance of additional focus on this region of the Pseudocrenilabrinae tree.

The remaining Oreochromini form two large clades. One contains the Barombi Mbo volcanic crater lake radiation and the riverine members of “*Sarotherodon*”. The Barombi Mbo radiation produced 11 species with diverse ecological adaptations, all of which are threatened by pollution, water extraction, and sedimentation today (Reid 1990). Internal relationships of this species flock remain difficult to resolve, but one of the better supported groupings is the commonly

recovered *Stomatepia mongo+mariae+pindu* species complex (Schliewen & Klee 2004, Wagner et al. 2012, Martin et al. 2015, Richards et al. 2018, Musilova et al. 2019 this study). A strongly supported *Myaka+Konia* grouping is recovered here (species tree) for the first time. High levels of gene heterogeneity at all nodes are consistent with rapid diversification as well as a history of gene flow both within the radiating species flock and between flock members and “*Sarotherodon*” from surrounding rivers (Fig. 3e, Schliewen & Klee 2004, Martin et al. 2015, Richards et al. 2018). Although sampling of riverine representatives of the primarily west central African “genus” *Sarotherodon* is minimal in our study, inclusion of the type species (*S. melanotheron*) confirms paraphyly of this assemblage (Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Schedel et al. 2019) and additional study with comprehensive sampling is necessary before taxonomic and nomenclatural stability can be attained for this economically important group.

The other main clade within Oreochromini consists of the pan-African, exclusively maternal mouthbrooding *Oreochromis* and *Alcolapia* radiation. A nested position for *Alcolapia* within *Oreochromis* is consistent with most molecular evidence (Seegers et al. 1999, Nagl et al. 2001, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Kavembe et al. 2014, Ford et al. 2015, 2019, Matschiner et al. 2017). *Alcolapia* diversified rapidly and produce four species in the hostile East African Soda Lakes Natron and Magadi (Ford et al. 2015). Species exhibit diverse ecologically-related phenotypes (Seegers & Tichy 1999, Tichy & Seegers 1999, Zaccara et al. 2014, Kavembe et al. 2015) despite restricted genetic differentiation and interspecific gene flow (Fig. 3e, Ford et al. 2015). Internal relationships are unresolvable and geographically inconsistent in our analyses. *A. grahami*, the only species from Lake Magadi, is nested among Lake Natron *Alcolapia* in both concatenated and species trees, which is in contrast to population genetic datasets that instead support *A. grahami* as sister to Lake Natron lineages (Seegers et al.

1999, Ford et al. 2015). Shared haplotypes and a grouping of some Lake Natron and *A. grahami* populations (Wilson et al. 2004, Zaccara et al. 2014, Ford et al. 2015) reveal a complex evolutionary history with enduring interspecific gene flow for *Alcolapia*. Initially, gene flow probably occurred when Lakes Natron and Magadi formed part of the same paleolake Orolonga. After the lakes separated additional gene flow seems to have been facilitated by fluctuating water levels that periodically connected diverging populations (Tichy & Seegers 1999, Seegers et al. 1999, Ford et al. 2015). Sampling of riverine *Oreochromis* is minimal in the present study, but despite almost complete coverage across the genus by Ford et al. (2019) mito-nuclear discord hindered resolution of the precise placement of the *Alcolapia* radiation (designated as a subgenus by Ford et al. 2019), and the placement of the type species, *O. hunteri*. As a result, taxonomic and nomenclatural stability within “*Oreochromis*” remains an outstanding problem.

Haplotilapiines: Boreotilapiines and Austrotilapiines

Alternative hypotheses exist for intertribal relationships of the substrate brooding former-tilapiines (previously included within the catch-all genus *Tilapia*). Various multilocus phylogenies supported a split of the substrate brooding former tilapiines (minus Pelmatolapiini), into two reciprocally monophyletic clades with limited distributional overlap: the boreotilapiines and austrotilapiines (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schlieven 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017). The boreotilapiines included the West/Central African Coelotilapiini, Heterotilapiini, Coptodonini and Gobiocichlini, while the austrotilapiines consisted of the Tilapiini, Steatocranini, and the EAR clade. Our grouping of Tilapiini+Steatocranini as sister to the EAR in the majority of analyses substantiates an austrotilapiine clade (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schlieven 2013, McMahan

et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019). However, phylogenomic data (Irisarri et al. 2018, this study) rejects a boreotilapiine grouping.

Although we find no support for reciprocal monophyly, the split of a mainly East African austrotilapiines clade from West/Central African lineages does not exclude historical vicariance as a driver of divergence. Some age estimates for the austrotilapiines are consistent with the onset of rifting in East Africa (Schwarzer et al. 2009, McMahan et al. 2013, Schedel et al. 2019), suggesting that plate tectonics and the ensuing shifts in hydrological systems promoted an early split between primarily western and eastern cichlid lineages.

Haplotilapiines: Former-Tilapiines: Coptodonini

Coptodonini is the first substrate brooding tribe to diverge after Oreochromini. Populations of the riverine *Coptodon guineensis* are believed to have seeded two *Coptodon* radiations in Cameroonian crater lakes, Ejagham (Dunz & Schliewen 2010, Stager et al. 2017, Poelstra et al. 2018) and Bermin (Stiassny et al. 1992, Schliewen et al. 1994). The present study includes six of nine described species from Lake Bermin, which form a strongly supported clade sister to *C. guineensis* (Martin et al. 2015). As in previous studies, internal relationships of the Bermin *Coptodon* species flock are characterized by very short branches, high gene tree heterogeneity and poor resolution.

Haplotilapiines: Former-Tilapiines: Heterotilapiini, Pelmatolapiini and Gobiocichlini

A close relationship between Coptodonini, Heterotilapiini and Coelotilapiini to the exclusion of other former-tilapiine tribes is supported by previous multilocus work (Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017). Unfortunately, we were

unable to include the monotypic Coelotilapiini (*Coelotilapia joka*) in the current study so are not able to comment on its placement, however our data consistently reject a grouping of Heterotilapiini with Coptodonini. Instead Heterotilapiini forms part of a clade that includes Pelmatolapiini (this study) and sometimes also Gobiocichlini (concatenated and species trees in this study, Irisarri et al. 2018).

The relationship of Pelmatolapiini to other haplotilapiine cichlids has remained elusive with. Conflicting results, often within the same multilocus study, suggest a close relationship to austrotilapiines, as sister to a boreotilapiine assemblage or some other rarely recovered placement (Klett & Meyer 2002, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schlieuwen 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019). Our robust placement of Pelmatolapiini in a clade with Heterotilapiini, with which it shares a range in west/central African coastal lowlands, is novel. Gene flow between Pelmatolapiini and other haplotilapiine species was previously suspected (Schwarzer et al. 2009). Our network analyses do not recover hybrid events involving Pelmatolapiini, but do infer hybridization between its close relative, Heterotilapiini, and Tilapiini (Fig. 3a).

Our placement of *Paragobiocichla irvinei* outside of *Steatocranus*, where it had been previously classified (Trewavas 1943), and instead within an expanded Gobiocichlini is consistent with previous molecular studies (Schwarzer et al. 2009, 2011, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schlieuwen, 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017) and its novel assignment to the monotypic genus, *Paragobiocichla* (Weiss et al. 2019). Placement within Gobiocichlini is biogeographically consistent as *P. irvinei* is restricted to the Volta River in proximity to the Cross and Niger rivers from which *Gobiocichla* is known. In contrast, *Steatocranini* is endemic to the west/central Congo basin and geographically closer to *Congolapia* and *Chilochromis*.

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: Former-Tilapiines: Tilapiini and Steatocranini

The close relationship between the former-tilapiine tribes Tilapiini and Steatocranini and the EAR clade is supported by numerous molecular datasets, but the exact arrangement of these three groups remains uncertain. Although our sampling of Tilapiini is limited we nonetheless find support for a Tilapiini+Steatocranini clade as sister to the EAR clade (concatenated, species and Sub1 [Fig. 3a] trees, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Weiss et al. 2015, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017). The most common alternative hypothesis proposed the early branching of Tilapiini followed by Steatocranini alone as sister to the EAR clade (Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019). Other less common arrangements have also been recovered (Fig. 3f, Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018).

The sharing of genetic material across suprageneric boundaries may be one reason for the recovery of a nonmonophyletic Tilapiini in our species tree and conflicting placements of the Tilapiini+Steatocranini and EAR clades amongst the former-tilapiine tribes (Schwarzer et al. 2009; Dunz & Schliewen 2013; Irisarri et al. 2018; Schedel et al. 2019). Both Tilapiini and Steatocranini species hybridized extensively with former-tilapiines (Fig. 3a,d) and members of the EAR clade (Fig. 3f, Irisarri et al. 2018), so much so that their inclusion in phylogenies sometimes jeopardizes the monophyly of the EAR clade (Klett & Meyer 2002, Weiss et al. 2015, Irisarri et al. 2018).

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade

The EAR clade includes well over 1500 species from rivers and lakes (Brawand et al. 2014), of which the East African great lakes Victoria, Malawi, and Tanganyika are best known. Species in the EAR clade exhibit diverse phenotypes, ecology, and behaviours, and several clades underwent

remarkable adaptive radiations, making the EAR cichlids a referential system for the study of diversification and adaptive evolution. However, despite their status as a model system for evolutionary research phylogenetic uncertainty persists. The monophyly of most EAR tribes and a tribal assemblage known as the MVhL Clade (Takahashi et al. 2001) are well established, but most other intertribal relationships have remained challenging.

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade: Non-MVhL Tribes

Three non-MVhL tribes are currently recognized, each of which are Lake Tanganyikan endemics: Trematocarini, Bathybatini and Boulengerochromini (Takahashi & Sota 2016). Several authors support the inclusion of *Hemibates* within Bathybatini (Poll 1986, Takahashi 2003, Wagner et al. 2012, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Kirchberger et al. 2012, Weiss et al. 2015, Irisarri et al. 2018), but alternative placements (Stiassny 1981) and molecular divergence of this genus has sometimes lead to the recognition of a fourth non-MVhL tribe, Hemibatini (Koblmüller et al. 2005, 2008). Regardless of details of tribal composition, it is generally accepted that the non-MVhL tribes are the earliest branching EAR lineages. However, it remains unclear how they are related to one another and whether one, two, or a clade consisting of all non-MVhL tribes, are sister to the remaining EAR (Nishida 1991, Klett & Meyer 2002, Salzburger et al. 2002, Takahashi 2003, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Koblmüller et al. 2005, Genner et al. 2007, Day et al. 2008, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021). Although we were unable to include *Trematocara* or *Hemibates* in the current study, our findings are consistent with reciprocal monophyly of non-MVhL tribes and the MVhL clade (Salzburger et al. 2002, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Wagner et al. 2012, Freidman

et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021). Interestingly, while multilocus phylogenies vary greatly in their support for alternative arrangements, studies based on a large number of loci converge on the same suprageneric topology, despite differences in the types of markers or methods (i.e., concatenated versus coalescent) used (Meyer et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021, this study). Our network analyses (Fig. 3a,f) and previous work (Weiss et al. 2015, Meyer et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018) indicate that hybridization near the base the EAR is a likely source of phylogenetic contention for these taxa.

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade: MVhL Clade

The MVhL clade, named for its inclusion of the Malawi (M), Victoria (V), Nishida's (1991) H-lineage (h) and Lamprologini (L) cichlids, consists of all EAR lineages minus Bathybatini (inclusive of *Hemibates*), Trematocarini, and Boulengerochromini, and is persistently recovered by molecular data (Nishida 1991, Sturmbauer & Meyer 1993, Kocher et al. 1995, Takahashi et al. 2001, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Genner et al. 2007, Day et al. 2008, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Dunz & Schliewen 2013, Friedman et al. 2013, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021, this study).

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade: MVhL Clade: Lamprologini

Lamprologini, the most species rich of Tanganyikan tribes and one of the few with riverine representation, is consistently retrieved as monophyletic in previous molecular studies (Kocher et al. 1995, Sturmbauer et al. 1994, 2010, Takahashi et al. 1998, Salzburger et al. 2002, Clabaut et al. 2005, Day et al. 2008, Wagner et al. 2012, Meyer et al. 2015, 2017, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi

& Sota 2016, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021). Unlike most other EAR tribes, the monophyly of Lamprologini is also strongly supported by morphological character data (Stiassny 1987, 1997, Lippitsch 1995). Either alone or in a clade with Eretmodini (see next section) Lamprologini is usually inferred to be sister to the remaining MVhL lineages.

The most basal divergence within our phylogenies splits Lamprologini into two large clades corresponding to species that exhibit a derived ossification of the labial cartilage forming the “ossified group” (Stiassny 1997, Day et al. 2007), and those that retain the plesiomorphic non-ossified condition of the cartilage. While only three exemplars of the “ossified group” were included (*Neolamprologus brevis*, *Altolamprologus compressiceps*, *Lamprologus lemairii*), our data corroborates previous work in strongly supporting monophyly of the “ossified” assemblage (Sturmbauer et al. 1994, Clabaut et al. 2005, Schelly et al. 2006, Day et al. 2007, Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Wagner et al. 2012, Meyer et al. 2015, Koblmüller et al. 2017, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019). Our exclusion of a few species (e.g., *Neolamprologus toae*, *N. tretocephalus*, and *N. cylindricus*) that have sometimes been found to diverge basally rather than grouping with other non-ossified taxa (Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Schelly et al. 2006) precludes us from reliably testing the monophyly of the non-ossified group.

Among sampled members of the non-ossified Lamprologini our data support the early branching of *Variabilichromis moori*+*N. sexfasciatus* and their sister relationship to a clade containing “*Julidochromis*”, *Chalinochromis*, *Telmatochromis*, the Congo River *Lamprologus*, and other “*Neolamprologus*” and “*Lamprologus*” species (Schelly et al. 2006, Day et al. 2007, Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021). This is in contrast to a previous hypothesis of *V. moori* as sister to all other Lamprologini

(Sturmbauer et al. 1994). In common with many previous studies we recover *N. furcifer* as a close relative of a *Julidochromis*+*Chalinochromis* complex (Sturmbauer et al. 1994, Day et al. 2007, Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021). Our analyses also include *N. mustax* in this clade (Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Ronco et al. 2021), but alternative multilocus hypotheses have that taxon occupying a more basal position amongst non-ossified taxa (Day et al. 2007, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017, Ronco et al. 2021). Finally, we infer a clade consisting of *Telmatochromis*, *N. pulcher*, *N. mondabu* (Ronco et al. 2021), and a clade consisting of the Congo River species, inclusive of a monophyletic LCR radiation (species tree).

While sampling of Tanganyikan Lamprologini is limited in the present study, sampling of riverine taxa is comprehensive. We provide strong support for a monophyletic Congo basin clade nested well within the Tanganyikan radiation, and provide the first phylogenomic evidence for a monophyletic LCR sub-clade (species and network trees) and possible gene flow (Fig. 3h) among riverine species. A nested placement of the Congo basin clade within the Lake Tanganyikan radiation is consistent with a secondary colonization of the main channel of the Congo River in a single dispersal event, probably via the Lukuga River (Sturmbauer et al. 1994, 2010, Salzburger et al. 2002, Day et al. 2008, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Schedel et al. 2019). A few multilocus phylogenies find a nested paraphyletic assemblage of some riverine species, which has led to a hypothesis of multiple dispersal events out of the lake and into the Congo basin (Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019).

Like most authors before us, we reject the monophyly of *Neolamprologus*, lake *Lamprologus* and *Julidochromis* (Stiassny 1997, Sturmbauer et al. 1994, Day et al. 2007, Wagner et al. 2012, Meyer et al. 2015, Koblmüller et al. 2017, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018,

Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021, our species tree), clearly indicating the need for additional work before a stable taxonomy and generic nomenclature for this tribe can be achieved. Interestingly, our analyses strongly support the placement of *J. marlieri* and *T. vitattus* with other members of their genus, consistent with other genomic findings (Ronco et al. 2021), which is in contrast to most multilocus and/or mitochondrial work that has these two species variously placed between different clades (Day et al. 2007, Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Wagner et al. 2012, Matschiner et al. 2017, Ronco et al. 2021).

Interspecific hybridization has been widely documented in Lamprologini (Schelly et al. 2006, Koblmüller et al. 2007, 2017, Nevado et al. 2009, this study). Our phylogenetic network analyses based on limited taxonomic sampling corroborate a few hybridization events (Fig. 3g). While our species tree strongly supports separate *Julidochromis* and *Telmatochromis* clades, our network analyses reveal gene flow between *T. vitattus* and a *J. marlieri*-containing clade, which may explain the placement of these taxa in close proximity in primarily mitochondrial phylogenies (Day et al. 2007, Matschiner et al. 2017, Ronco et al. 2021). Gene flow between *J. dickfeldi* and *Chalinochromis marlieri* may further explain the occasional paraphyly *Julidochromis* (Day et al. 2007, Matschiner et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021, species tree). Additional instances of interspecific gene flow were detected in lake and river taxa as well, albeit with lower support (Fig. 3f). Interspecific gene flow is therefore a likely source of the topological discordances discussed here and elsewhere. Our documentation of short internal branches and elevated gene heterogeneity at many nodes provide further support for rapid diversification and/or hybridization both in Lake Tanganyika and Congo basin Lamprologini.

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade: MVhL Clade: H-Lineage

Nishida (1991) named the MVhL clade minus Lamprologini the H-Lineage, and since that time its monophyly has been highly debated. Almost every intertribal topology has been recovered for the MVhL clade, with some studies corroborating (Meyer et al. 2015, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021) and many others refuting (Kocher et al. 1995, Salzburger et al. 2002, Clabaut et al. 2005, Day et al. 2008, Wagner et al. 2012, Weiss et al. 2015, Sturmbauer et al. 2010, Matschiner et al. 2017) the existence of an H-Lineage. Most of the studies that dispute the H-Lineage do so as a result of either grouping Eretmodini with Lamprologini (Kocher et al. 1995, Takahashi 2003, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Day et al. 2008, Schwarzer et al. 2009, Wagner et al. 2012, Dunz & Schlieven 2013, Weiss et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017) or inferring Eretmodini as sister to Lamprologini+the remaining H-Lineage tribes (Salzburger et al. 2002, 2005). This commonly recovered alternative grouping of H-lineage tribes minus Eretmodini has been referred to as the C-lineage by Clabaut et al. (2005) and subsequent authors.

Our dataset provides unequivocal support for an H-lineage, but we are only able to confidently infer some of its intertribal relationships. The deepest nodes are poorly resolved while the shallower groupings of Ectodini+Limnochromini, Perissodini+Cyprichromini, and Eretmodini+Haplochromini are robust in both concatenated and species trees. Only a handful of previous studies agree with an Ectodini+Limnochromini clade (Nishida 1991, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021), as most others group Ectodini or Limnochromini with other tribes (Sturmbauer & Meyer 1993, Kocher et al. 1995, Salzburger et al. 2002, Takahashi 2003, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Day et al. 2008, Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, 2017, Matschiner et al. 2017, Ronco et al. 2021, our Sub6 and Sub7 network analyses: Fig. 3f,g). A close relationship between Perissodini and Cyprichromini has also

been noted in previous studies (Muschick et al. 2012, Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021). Various relationships have been proposed for Cyphotilapiini with the most common being as sister to Limnochromini (Kocher et al. 1995, Salzburger et al. 2002, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, 2017). Our network analyses are consistent with a Limnochromini+Cyphotilapiini grouping (Fig. 3f,g) and suggest that gene flow between Limnochromini and Ectodini may underly their grouping in species and concatenated analyses here and elsewhere. Our unstable placement of Cyphotilapiini as sister to all other H-lineage tribes has been recovered in few other studies (Wagner et al. 2012, Irisarri et al. 2018). Finally, our firm placement of Eretmodini as sister to Haplochromini is widely supported amongst phylogenies that infer the H-lineage, particularly those based on mainly nuclear data (Nishida 1991, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, 2017, Weiss et al. 2015, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021, see Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021 for alternate relationships based on mitochondrial data).

As with the non-MVhL tribes, phylogenomic studies appear to be arriving at some consensus regarding H-Lineage relationships. Whereas multilocus datasets exhibit widespread disagreement, phylogenomics has converged on a few tribal groupings consistent with those recovered here (Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Ronco et al. 2021). However, these large datasets continue to disagree on the interrelationships of some inferred groupings. Very short branches and network analyses indicate a history of incomplete lineage sorting (ILS) resulting from rapid diversification and hybridization (Takahashi et al. 2001, Koblmüller et al. 2010, Meier et al. 2017, Weiss et al. 2015, Irisarri et al. 2018, Fig. 3a-h). Continued efforts to date the cichlid phylogeny will allow us to better elucidate whether the high levels of gene heterogeneity observed

here and elsewhere (Meyer et al. 2015) is mostly due to explosive radiation following colonization or to extensive gene flow in a hybrid swarm that came together following lake formation (Seehausen 2004, Weiss et al. 2015, Schedel et al. 2019).

Haplotilapiines: Austrotilapiini: EAR Clade: MVhL Clade: H-Lineage: Haplochromini

Haplochromini is the largest and most widespread of the Pseudocrenilabrinae tribes. Our sampling within this tribe is far from comprehensive, however we corroborate the placement of *Orthochromis sensu stricto* from the Malagarasi drainage system as sister to all other Haplochromini (Day et al. 2008, Wagner et al. 2012, Weiss et al. 2015, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021). Alternative groupings of the Malagarasi *Orthochromis* with Tanganyikan H-Lineage tribes are believed to be the result of extensive interspecific hybridization (Salzburger et al. 2005, Weiss et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017). The Malagarasi River is one of the main tributaries of Lake Tanganyika and the early divergence of its endemics within Haplochromini suggests that the Malagarasi River may have been the portal through which a Tanganyikan ancestor escaped the lake to invade and diversify in surrounding habitats.

Following the divergence of *Ctenochromis sensu stricto* (represented in our study by the type species, *C. pectoralis*) Haplochromini is partitioned into two large clades in concatenated and species trees. One includes representation of “*Orthochromis*” from the Luapula-Mweru-Lualaba drainage (LML-*Orthochromis*, following Weiss et al. 2015, but see Schedel et al. 2019), *Pseudocrenilabrus* (Friedman et al. 2013, Weiss et al. 2015, Schedel et al. 2019), the serranochromines and the small Lake Fwa radiation (see below). An association between *Pseudocrenilabrus* and the LML-*Orthochromis* (Dunz & Schlieven 2013, Weiss et al. 2015,

Ronco et al. 2021), and their close relationship to serranochromines (Meyer et al. 2015, Weiss et al. 2015, Ronco et al. 2021) is strongly favoured by our data.

The species rich and morphologically diverse serranochromines (Haplochromini) are currently mainly restricted to riverine habitats. However, biogeographic and geological records indicate that extant species are vestiges of an ancient Pleistocene radiation in Lake palaeo-Magadikgadi, the extent of which may have been comparable to the radiations in the East African great lakes (Joyce et al. 2005). It is hypothesized that by around 2000 year ago the lake had mostly dried leaving behind only those lineages that were able to colonize the surrounding rivers. The recovery of a monophyletic assemblage of serranochromines with short internal branches is consistent with rapid localized diversification. Closely related to the serranochromines is a small, but morphologically diversified, radiation of 5 species endemic to Lake Fwa in the Kasai basin (Roberts & Kullander 1994) which, with the inclusion of the neighbouring riverine “*T.*” *stigmatogenys* as sister to “*T.*” *brauschi*, is resolved here as monophyletic with strong support in both the concatenated and species trees. Like other radiations in our phylogeny, the Lake Fwa clade is characterized by short internal branches and high gene heterogeneity consistent with rapid divergence. Gene flow between Lake Fwa and nearby riverine lineages (Fig. 3g) is also inferred.

The other main haplochromine clade, sometimes referred to as the “modern haplochromines” (Salzburger et al. 2005), consists of species from Lakes Tanganyika (formerly referred to the Tropheini, and herein referred to as tropheines), lakes Malawi and Victoria basins, and a few species from neighboring lakes and rivers (Salzburger et al. 2005, Weiss et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021). The tropheine assemblage was once classified as its own tribe (Poll 1986), but molecular data provide overwhelming support for its nested position within Haplochromini, most often as sister to the remaining members of the

clade (Nishida et al. 1991, Sturmbauer & Meyer 1993, Kocher et al. 1995, Takahashi et al. 2001, Salzburger et al. 2002, 2005, Takahashi 2003, Clabaut et al. 2005, 2007, Genner et al. 2007, Day et al. 2008, Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, Meyer et al. 2015, Weiss et al. 2015, Matschiner et al. 2017, Takahashi & Sota 2016, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021, this study). A riverine ancestor is believed to have entered Lake Tanganyika and radiated rapidly in parallel with radiations already underway in Tanganyika (Salzburger et al. 2005). A monophyletic tropheine assemblage with short deep branches is consistent with rapid radiation presumably upon entering Lake Tanganyika.

The nested placement of the Lake Malawi and Victoria radiations within the “modern haplochromines” confirms that these radiations were seeded by lineages with origins in Lake Tanganyika (Salzburger et al. 2005). Either the Malagarasi or Rusizi River are believed to be the portal through which an ancestor colonized the East African great lakes. The geologic history of both rivers includes repeated transient connections to Lake Tanganyika and water bodies further to the north, such as those of the Lake Victoria basin (Danley et al. 2012). Furthermore, close relationships between the great lakes fishes and species from both river systems has been noted on several occasions (Salzburger et al. 2005, Wagner et al. 2012, Friedman et al. 2013, Matschiner et al. 2017, Weiss et al. 2015, Irisarri et al. 2018, Schedel et al. 2019, Ronco et al. 2021, this study).

We document elevated gene heterogeneity and several phylogenetic networks throughout Haplochromini, consistent with a history of rapid radiation and extensive hybridization. Riverine lineages in particular, are thought to have hybridized widely with lacustrine ancestors, which is supported here by our inference of networks between riverine *Orthochromis*, *Pseudocrenilabrus* and serranochromines and other riverine or lacustrine lineages (Fig. 3g,h) . In so doing, it appears that riverine cichlids may have acted as “transporters of genomic variation” that facilitated rapid

adaptation during the explosive radiations of haplochromines in several East African lake systems (Loh et al. 2013, Weiss et al. 2015, Meyer et al. 2017, Irisarri et al. 2018).

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Figure S1. Maps showing the distribution of individual Pseudocrenilabrinae tribes in and around Africa. Colours are similar to those used to denote tribes in Fig. 2. The world map at the lower-right corner shows the distribution of all cichlids (shaded regions), with an emphasis on Pseudocrenilabrinae (darker shading) in the red box. As in Fig. 1, red text is used to indicate tribes that were not sampled in this study and * denotes tribes with disputed taxonomic status.